

SPORTS VOCABULARY OF THE TURKMEN LANGUAGE LEXICO-THEMATIC GROUPS

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At the inauguration ceremony of the President of Turkmenistan on March 19, 2022, the Honorable President Serdar Gurbangulyevich Berdimuhamedov said: "The main place belongs to the development of mass sports and youth policy in our independent country" [1]. Today, sports, which have become an integral part of people's healthy life, are the focus of attention of scientists working in various fields, and at the same time, the language of sports is of great interest to linguists. While studying the words that make up the sports lexicon of the Turkmen language in every way, it is important to analyze their semantic relationship with each other.

The lexical system of any language forms a complex structure, in which lexical units have different meaning relations. Therefore, one of the main tasks of lexicology is to systematize those lexical units by dividing them into thematic groups. It is considered the most convenient way to study (declare) large-scale and diverse lexical material by thematic groups [2].

The sports lexicon of the Turkmen language is divided into seven lexical-thematic groups. They are: names of sports, names of participants in sports competitions and games, names of sports equipment, training tools, names of sports clothing and protective equipment, names of sports facilities and fields, names of acts and actions, names of sports levels, symbols, awards.

One of the largest lexical-thematic groups of our analyzed lexicon is the names of sports. More than a hundred words belonging to this group have been registered. We have divided the names of sports into the following thematic groups according to their characteristics, condition, goal to be achieved, similarity of rules, venue, sports equipment used, active mobility, logic of passive thinking (summarization, correct and quick calculation of opportunities): 1) equestrian sports; 2) athletics; 3) technical sports; 4) gymnastics; 5) head-to-head martial arts; 6) racket sports; 7) team sports games; 8) water sports; 9) skiing and snowboarding sports; 10) bicycle sports; 11) sports related to hitting, throwing; 12) multi-type competitions; 13) logical thinking (concentrating, calculating possibilities correctly and quickly).

The words belonging to the lexical-thematic group named names of participants in sports competitions and games consist of common and special names. Special names differ according to the position of athletes on the field of play, their affiliation to a certain sports competition, their role in the competition, the sports vehicle they drive or the sports equipment they use. Words belonging to this lexical-thematic group are more numerous than the ones mentioned above. Words belonging to the lexical-thematic group named names of sports equipment and training tools are distinguished by their diversity. The sports lexicon of the Turkmen language includes words related to lexical-thematic groups such as the names of sports clothes and defense equipment, the names of sports facilities and fields, the names of actions and actions, the names of sports levels, symbols and awards, but they are significant in terms of meaning.

As can be seen from the analysis, it is possible to divide the units related to the sports lexicon of the Turkmen language into lexical-thematic groups according to their meaning. Dividing these lexical units into thematic groups helps to visualize the structure of the language of sports and to reliably understand their meaning.

REFERENCES

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